

SELECTION AND IMPLEMENTATION OF ADAPTATION INTERVENTIONS IN SOUTH AFRICA AND ZIMBABWE

Deliverable 4.8

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Author(s)	Shobna Sawry, Celeste Madondo (Wits RHI, South Africa); Tapiwa Nyakabau, Brian Sibanda, Fortunate Machingura (CeSHHAR Zimbabwe)
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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition/Description
ANC	Antenatal clinic
CeSHHAR	Centre for Sexual Health and HIV/AIDS Research (Zimbabwe)
CHC	Community health centre
CRM	Community Resource Mapping
CSO	Civil society organisation
EU	European Union
GAD	General Anxiety Disorder
HAPI	Heat Adaptation for Pregnant Women and Infants
HCW	Healthcare worker
IDI	In-depth interview
KII	Key informant interview
MNCH	Maternal, neonatal and child Health
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
OHS	Occupational Health Standard
PNC	Postnatal care
PPW	Pregnant and post-partum women
SA	South Africa
SEM	Socio-Ecological Model
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
ToC	Theory of Change
WHO	World Health Organization
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

Global temperatures are rising, with Africa emerging as one of the most vulnerable regions to climate change and extreme heat events. Healthcare workers face heightened risks from heat exposure due to poor working environments, including inadequate ventilation and lack of cooling systems in many public health facilities. Their work is often physically demanding, requiring long hours with the use of heavy protective clothing further exacerbating heat stress. As a result, heat exposure can strain both physical and emotional coping capacities, leading to impaired performance, compromised quality of care, increased absenteeism, and lower job satisfaction. Thus, the urgent need for targeted contextual heat adaptation and mitigation interventions.

Co-design, an effective collaborative approach, was used to identify and prioritize targeted context-specific heat adaptation interventions. The process brought together researchers, community members, facility managers, policymakers, and other stakeholders, and facilitated equal participation to share knowledge and refine multi-component heat adaptation interventions in South Africa and Zimbabwe. The approach consisted of workshops in South Africa and Zimbabwe. The findings from the baseline research were shared with participants to guide discussions and enable identification and prioritisation of heat adaptation interventions for health facilities.

All outputs were refined, leading to the agreement on approximately 20 context-specific heat adaptation interventions across four domains in both countries. In South Africa, these interventions include behavioural adaptations supported through the employment of a facility-based heat champion responsible for provision of personal cooling items, water, health talks, ventilation checks, monitoring heat stress symptoms and conduct of educational sessions, among other duties. Built environment adaptations include the installation of energy efficient air conditioners and water filter coolers, application of reflective roof

paint and installation of ceiling insulation. Lastly, nature-based solutions include planting trees around the facility. In Zimbabwe, behavioural adaptation measures include, provision of personal cooling kits, adjusting work schedules, training on waste segregation, and developing facility guidance to support heat-health training. Built environment modifications include installation of energy efficient air conditioners, application of reflective roof paint, installation of ceiling insulation and establishing a demonstration site showcasing heat-resilient infrastructure, while nature-based interventions include planting trees around the facility. Additionally, the Theory of Change and logical frameworks for each country were finalised, providing a structured foundation for implementation which constitutes the next phase of the study.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The document outlines the selection and implementation of adaptation interventions co-designed in South Africa and Zimbabwe in July 2024 and January 2025, respectively. It provides insights into the co-production process, presents the Theory of Change (ToC) for both countries, highlights progress to date, and outlines the timeline for full implementation.

1.2 Relation to other project work

This deliverable builds on earlier work within HIGH Horizons, shaping the trajectory of the HIGH Horizons heat-related adaptation activities. It is strongly connected to and informed by the findings from two sub-studies in South Africa, Zimbabwe and Sweden as described in deliverables *D2.8 – Environmental exposures in health facilities* (Toftum 2024) and *D2.10 – Health workers impact baseline analysis*, both dated February 2024. The health worker baseline assessment faced delays due to ethical clearance of the study protocol, health facility approvals to start data collection, and the need to conduct the baseline assessment in both hot and cold seasons to get more insights in the impact of heat exposure on health workers. Deliverable D2.10 will be updated in August 2025, including the preliminary findings from Sweden.

Deliverable *D3.6 – Report on selection of alternative adaptation interventions* outlined the process to co-develop evidence-informed and context-specific climate adaptation interventions in health facilities. However, the final co-design process and selection of adaptation interventions are detailed in this report.

After implementation, an endline study and process evaluation will assess the effectiveness and the cost-consequences of these interventions in South Africa and Zimbabwe. The study protocol for the evaluation is described in deliverable *D5.4 – Protocol and ethics approval for health facility adaptation interventions*. Ethical

clearance has already been obtained. The evaluation findings will be described in two reports: *D5.5 – Evaluation of experiences and effectiveness of adaptation in health facilities* (August 2025) and *D5.6 – Analysis of cost-benefits of heat adaptation interventions on workers' health and productivity* (March 2026).

This deliverable also links to the selection and implementation of mitigation interventions described in deliverable *D4.9 – Selection and implementation of carbon mitigation interventions in Kenya, Zimbabwe & South Africa*, as adaptation and mitigation interventions in South Africa and Zimbabwe are integrated and implemented simultaneously, though the evaluation will be conducted separately.

2 Background

The frequency and intensity of temperature extremes, high ambient temperature (above the 90th percentile), and heatwaves have increased in the past four decades and are projected to continue rising. The increase is to such an extent that current average global temperatures are reported to be 1.1 °C higher than pre-industrial period (Chersich et al., 2020; Hoegh-Guldberg et al., 2019; Turek-Hankins et al., 2021). Crossing the heat threshold (over 1.0 °C) has severely impacted natural and biological systems but pertinently accumulating evidence shows strong links to adverse human health outcomes and mortality (Hoegh-Guldberg et al., 2019). By 2100, it is estimated that 54% of the global population will be exposed to more than 20 days of deadly heat annually (Zhao et al., 2021).

Africa has been shown to be vulnerable to climate change and growing extreme heat events. Over the past decade, heat extremes (above 45 °C) were observed in some regions of the continent such as North Africa and South Africa (Iyakaremye, 2021). Studies also show that mean temperatures in regions such as central Africa and the sub-tropics have risen twice the global rate (Almazroui et al., 2020; Iyakaremye, 2021). Machine learning and mathematical modelling techniques

project an increase in frequency and intensity of extremely hot days (when maximum temperature exceeds 35 °C) across the African continent, which poses a great challenge because of inadequate disaster management plans, limited adaptive capacities, poor land use, and existing socio-economic inequalities (Almazroui et al., 2020; Iyakaremye, 2021).

Healthcare Workers (HCWs) are at high risk of adverse outcomes due to heat exposure and are at a higher risk of heat exposure due to poor working environments. Many public health facilities in low and middle-income settings do not have optimal structural features and have poor or no centralised air-cooling or ventilation systems. Secondly, HCWs globally often engage in exertional work over long working hours, in heavy, and warm personal protective clothing, further increasing their exposure to heat. With heat exposure, physical and emotional coping capacities may become strained, leading to poor work performance, poor delivery of care to clients, increased rates of absenteeism, and poor job satisfaction. In South Africa, evidence already shows that sub-optimal working conditions are some of the key reasons HCWs are dissatisfied with their jobs (Payne et al., 2020). Additionally, repeated exposure to extreme indoor heat is likely to lead to heat-related illness and possibly hospitalization for those who are physiologically vulnerable (such as those with chronic conditions) which may in turn further strain the healthcare system. HCWs in labour wards and neonatal care units are required to be quick in their response and reactions under strict guidelines (in cases of obstetrical and neonatal emergencies) otherwise the health of patients may be compromised. An added burden of extreme heat exposure to already strained HCWs – facing long working hours, occupational burnout, stressful social and environmental conditions among other issues (Myers et al., 2011; Turek-Hankins et al., 2021) - is a huge concern.

Existing research on occupational heat exposure focuses only on outdoor and manual labourers such as agricultural and factory workers, because of exposure

to direct heat and a dress code that may impair heat regulation (Flouris et al 2018). Current evidence concerning other occupations and heat exposure includes a systematic review conducted on 111 studies, which shows that 35% of individuals working under environmental heat stress conditions experienced heat strain (i.e., physiological consequences, such as core body temperature $>38^{\circ}\text{C}$, ≥ 1 occupational heat strain symptom, such as serum creatinine concentration of $>1,2$ mg/dL, heat-associated self-reported nausea or vomiting) and 30% experienced reduced productivity (defined as loss of labour time, performance, or absence from work due to occupational heat strain). However, no study included, focused on heat stress conditions among HCWs globally (Flouris et al 2018).

Climate change and heat impact policies in South Africa, Zimbabwe and Sweden are impeded by major gaps in surveillance and observational research, including for essential occupations such as HCWs.

3 Site-specific descriptions

This section summarises key characteristics of healthcare facilities in the study, including location and facility type.

3.1 Implementation sites in South Africa

In South Africa, the catchment areas of the two facilities are situated in Region 6 in the Tshwane district; Gauteng Province. The hottest months of the year are in the region selected for the study are usually December, January and February, and the highest, minimum, and mean temperatures are: 30°C , 17°C , and 23°C , respectively. Whereas the coldest months of the year are usually June/July, and the highest, minimum, and mean temperatures are $20/21^{\circ}\text{C}$, 5°C , and 13°C , respectively.

Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre. Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre is a vital healthcare facility located in Mamelodi East, Pretoria, Gauteng, South Africa. Operating 24 hours a day, seven days a week, the centre provides accessible and comprehensive healthcare services to the Mamelodi East community and surrounding areas and serves a population of approximately 261 989. The facility offers a wide range of primary healthcare services, including women's health, child health, HIV/AIDS care, tuberculosis treatment, sexually transmitted infections management, antenatal care, obstetrics, chronic disease management, and curative services. On average, about 250 newly pregnant women attend their first antenatal care visit at this facility every month with 74 deliveries. About 80 healthcare workers are employed in the antenatal care and delivery wards.

The centre has been recognized for its excellence by the National Health Department for ensuring over 2 000 patients, including those with HIV/AIDS, consistently receive their medication, significantly reducing default rates and improving health outcomes. This achievement reflects its commitment to delivering high-quality, patient-centered care.

Mamelodi Regional Hospital. Mamelodi Regional Hospital, located at Mamelodi East, Gauteng, South Africa, is a public healthcare facility serving the Mamelodi community and surrounding areas. The hospital is situated about 3.5 km from Stanza Bopape CHC and is a referral centre for patients requiring a higher level of care including pregnant women with obstetric emergencies from Stanza Bopape CHC and other surrounding feeder clinics. The hospital has a catchment population of 334 577 and offers the following services: clinical specialties in fields of Medicine, Surgery, Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Paediatrics, Psychiatry, Radiology, Emergency Medical Services, Trauma, non-communicable diseases and clinical management of HIV/AIDS and TB (including preventative therapy), screening and laboratory (e.g., cervical screening and colposcopy services, HIV

testing (ELISA and PCR) and TB (including drug-resistant TB). With a capacity of 500 beds, the hospital handles approximately 3 500 casualty patients and 10 000 outpatients monthly. On average, the hospital attends to about 780 deliveries, with 108 healthcare workers employed in the antenatal care and delivery wards.

Mamelodi Regional Hospital remains a vital healthcare provider, continuously striving to enhance service delivery and operational efficiency.

3.2 Implementation sites in Zimbabwe

Mt Darwin District Hospital. Mt Darwin Hospital is a key public healthcare facility located in the Mt Darwin District of Mashonaland Central Province, Zimbabwe. Serving a predominantly rural population, the hospital plays a critical role in providing essential healthcare services in the province and country. The facility is positioned to address the healthcare needs of local communities, including vulnerable groups such as women, children, and the elderly, who often face barriers to accessing medical care due to poverty and limited infrastructure serving on average 24 218 patients annually. Mt Darwin district hospital acts as primary care and referral facility for the whole district which has an estimated population of 1 384 891 (Male 681 313 & Female 703 578).

The hospital offers a range of medical services, including general outpatient care, maternal and child health services, emergency care, surgical procedures, and treatment for infectious diseases such as malaria, tuberculosis, and HIV/AIDS. It also supports public health initiatives, including immunization programmes and health education campaigns, to improve community health outcomes. Despite its vital role, Mt Darwin Hospital faces significant challenges, including chronic underfunding, frequent shortages of medical supplies, and unreliable energy and water supplies, which hinder its ability to deliver consistent and high-quality care.

Chitse Healthcare Facility. Chitse Healthcare Facility (commonly referred to as Chitse Clinic) is a rural healthcare centre located 16km from Mount Darwin District

Hospital, serving a predominantly agrarian and underserved population. Situated in a region characterized by limited infrastructure and economic challenges, the clinic is a critical provider of primary healthcare services to the local community, including remote villages that rely on its services for basic medical care. The facility plays a vital role in addressing the healthcare needs of vulnerable groups, such as women, children, and the elderly, who often face significant barriers to accessing healthcare due to poverty and geographic isolation.

The clinic provides essential healthcare services, including outpatient care, maternal and child health services, immunization programmes, and treatment for common illnesses such as malaria and diarrheal diseases. It also actively participates in national health campaigns, such as the Mass Drug Administration for bilharzia and intestinal worms, which are critical to improving public health outcomes in the region. Additionally, Chitse Clinic serves as a first point of contact for emergency cases, which are referred to larger hospitals such as Mt Darwin hospital for advanced care when necessary.

A key strength of Chitse Clinic is its strong community engagement. Healthcare workers at the facility actively engage with the community to disseminate accurate health information, promote preventive care, and encourage the utilization of available health services. This approach has helped build trust and improve health-seeking behaviours among the local population, ensuring that the clinic's services are effectively utilized.

Chitse Clinic faces numerous challenges, including inadequate funding, shortages of medical supplies, and unreliable access to electricity and clean water, which limit its ability to provide consistent and high-quality care.

Dotito Rural Healthcare Facility. Dotito Rural Health Centre is a key healthcare facility located in Dotito, a growth point within the Mount Darwin District of Mashonaland Central Province, Zimbabwe. Situated in a region characterized by limited infrastructure and economic challenges, the facility serves a

predominantly rural and underserved population. Dotito Rural Health Centre plays a critical role in providing primary healthcare services to the local community, including remote villages that rely on its services for basic medical care. The facility is particularly vital for vulnerable groups, such as women, children, and the elderly, who often face significant barriers to accessing healthcare due to poverty and geographic isolation.

The health centre collaborates closely with village health workers and local organizations to deliver essential health services directly to the community. This includes growth monitoring, nutritional support, and health education programmes. These efforts have strengthened the relationship between the facility and the community, ensuring that healthcare services are accessible and utilized effectively. Even with its important role, Dotito Rural Health Centre encounters several challenges, such as insufficient funding, a lack of medical supplies, and inconsistent access to electricity and clean water.

4 Methodology for baseline data collection

We employed several methodologies to collect the relevant baseline data to inform our co-design process. These are described briefly below.

Participant Observations: This process involved careful observation of the work and structural environment, and attention to daily activities within relevant clinics or wards, and informal conversations at the health facility. Key focus areas included the organization of care, interpersonal dynamics among staff and between HCWs and patients, and interactions with the built environment—such as points of refuge, relief, and discomfort. The researcher also assessed signs of stress, work practices, and the quality and respectfulness of care. Through observations and informal discussions with staff, the study captured how HCWs

experience and respond to heat, as well as the coping strategies they have developed.

Photovoice: Photovoice was used as a participatory research method that empowered individuals to document and share their lived experiences through photography. We used an adapted Photovoice methodology to engage 14 women (7 pregnant women and 7 new mothers) living in an informal settlement in Tshwane district, South Africa. Purposive sampling was employed to recruit a diverse mix of ages, and both primi- and multiparous women. We held two structured workshops with the women. The first involved reflective discussions about navigating heat exposure in their homes and communities, coupled with training in basic photography skills. Over two weeks, the women captured images on heat-related themes using a disposable camera or their mobile phones. In a follow-up workshop, a printed selection of images from the women were used as the basis for creating appropriate heat-health messages. All photographs were assessed by three members of the study team, who independently ranked each image using a set of pre-determined criteria (responsive to project themes, quality, narrative quality). The most evocative and relevant images were curated into a final set for further discussion at the follow-up workshop. We present a reflection of their experiences of heat and the barriers they face, as documented through their photographs.

Thermal monitoring: Thermal exposure assessments were to measure the health facility building's thermal environment, to make observations to characterize the building and its installations, and to examine how the buildings and their occupants can adapt to moderate their thermal exposure. The building thermal environment was characterized through monitoring: air temperature, globe temperature, and air humidity. Thermal monitoring was conducted continuously throughout the study period.

Key Informant Interviews (KII): These interviews aimed to understand key informants' perspectives on the impact and severity of heat exposure and climate change in their respective settings, as well as their views on the feasibility and acceptability of heat adaptation interventions. Key informant interviews were conducted with health facility managers, district health managers, clinic committee members, chair of the research committee, local councillor, member of the mayoral committee, youth motivators, regional managers, and community leaders to gather critical contextual insights for developing effective heat adaptation strategies.

In-depth Interviews (IDI): This qualitative data collection method involved conducting one-on-one discussions with participants to explore their experiences, perceptions, and insights in detail. Participants were purposively sampled from HCWs working in maternal and newborn care and included a mix of genders, ages, and roles (midwife, obstetrician, etc.). It was conducted using a semi-structured interview guide, conducted with enrolled healthcare workers HCWs to gain a deeper understanding of their experiences, challenges, and adaptations related to heat exposure in the workplace.

Surveys: This structured data collection method was used to gather information on participants' experiences, perceptions, and wellbeing. An electronic survey was administered through a tablet among healthcare workers. Surveys were conducted in the hot season (November – January) and in the cooler season (June - August). In total, we aimed to enrol 160 HCWs in the survey (80 per country). We aimed to enrol the same participants in the first and second surveys where possible. In this study, the survey assessed healthcare workers' wellbeing (using the WHO Wellbeing Index for Health Workers), psychological status (Cohen's Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-4) and General Anxiety Disorder (GAD-7), perceived heat stress and thermal comfort, as well as their perceptions of their health status and working conditions.

Time-motion assessment: Our time-motion methodology involved direct, continuous observation to track workflow, interactions, and disruptions in healthcare facilities. It helped assess how heat impacts efficiency and the quality of care provided by healthcare workers. By closely monitoring activities over time, this approach also captured subtle yet important aspects, such as worker fatigue and patient interactions, that might otherwise have gone unnoticed. Time motion assessments were conducted in maternity wards in two hospitals, and a community healthcare centre with approximately 800-1000 deliveries per year each (1 in Zimbabwe, 2 in South Africa). A list of all potentially eligible nurses was drawn up and participants were randomly selected using a computer-generated random number sequence and enrolled into the study following informed consent procedures.

Transect walk: Transect walk was used as a participatory method in Zimbabwe, to understand women's living environments, day-to-day practices, resources, and spatial parameters in the areas that they live in. The objectives of this method were to gain an understanding about how pregnant and post-partum women live in their day-to-day environment, in particular, how the behaviours that were targeted in this study fitted in their daily routine and what barriers and opportunities they encounter in performing these. The participants were recruited through antenatal and child vaccination appointments targeting 5 third trimester and 5 post-partum women. The researchers met with the participants individually and explained the procedures of the transect activity. The participants designated a meeting point, generally their home and the researcher-participant pair moved out from this point following the prompts of the transect data collection tool. This was essentially a walking interview that allowed the researcher to explore and ask questions, drawing out details and aspects of the surroundings that the research participant would not notice anymore due to familiarity.

5 Co-design of adaptation interventions

Co-design is increasingly being adopted across various sectors to foster the joint development of services and products by blending lived experiences with professional expertise, ensuring that all stakeholders, including programme beneficiaries, are valued as equal partners in the process. Co-design describes a collaborative process involving researchers, community groups, managers, policymakers, service users, and others to design, share, and negotiate knowledge, wisdom, and experience for improving service delivery and quality of life. Key elements of co-design include:

- **Broad applicability:** Co-design is relevant across different sectors, aiming to understand diverse needs and develop appropriate solutions.
- **Needs-driven:** Emphasizes understanding the lived experiences of affected populations, which in this case were pregnant and postpartum women, healthcare workers, and households.
- **Inclusive participation:** Involves stakeholders from multiple levels, including local communities, Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), and different tiers of government (local, provincial, and national). This ensures representation from not only the primary beneficiaries but also from wider communities and institutions.
- **Equal decision-making:** Ensures that all stakeholders have an equal voice in shaping interventions by providing a platform that effectively manages power dynamics and facilitates inclusive decision-making during the workshop.
- **Solution-oriented:** Goes beyond gathering opinions, involving stakeholders in crafting actionable interventions through a combination of professional and lived experience.
- **Implementation focus:** Prioritizes translating concepts into actionable plans. The identified interventions were used to develop the project log-

frame, which serves as the foundation for the implementation plan and results measurement framework.

5.1 Co-design process in South Africa

❖ Overview of approach

The purpose of the co-design workshops was to enable researchers and stakeholders to work as equals to conceive and agree upon the most effective methods for designing and delivering a multi-component heat adaptation intervention. In South Africa, the co-design process was conducted over a 3-day workshop where participants collaboratively interpreted preliminary findings derived from comprehensive ethnographic observations, in-depth interviews, key informant interviews and thermal modelling; identified and prioritise interventions based on specific criteria. The research teams in South Africa (Wits RHI) are concurrently involved in a [Wellcome Trust funded project called HAPI](#), which focus on heat adaptation at individual, household, facility and community level. To maximise resources and impact, the co-design of activities involved both the HIGH Horizons and HAPI projects. The co-design workshops for the combined HIGH Horizons and HAPI projects brought together 122 participants from diverse sectors to collaboratively identify and prioritize interventions. This included pregnant and postpartum women (PPW) and heads of households from the target communities, healthcare workers, community representatives including leaders, CSOs, representatives from various government institutions and academia.

❖ Baseline data synthesis

Prior to the co-design workshop, data synthesis sessions were held in July 2024, in preparation for the co-design workshop. This was done as a collaboration by the research teams in South Africa and Zimbabwe, with support and input from HAPI and HIGH Horizons consortium partners. The data synthesis integrated findings from the data collected in the HIGH Horizons project and the formative stage of

the HAPI study. All methods used are described in detail in Section 4. This includes data from:

- Pregnant and postpartum women (ethnographic observations, photovoice, serial IDIs, diary accounts of thermal experiences, physiological activity and sleep data collected from Fitbit Inspire 3 trackers, personal iButton DS1922 temperature monitors, and household thermal monitors);
- Health workers (participant observations, IDIs, core body temperature monitors, time-motion assessments and surveys);
- Facilities (facility thermal simulations, KIIs with key health facility staff, facility-based carbon emissions monitoring);
- Communities (Key Informant Interviews with policymakers, community leaders and traditional leaders).

These outputs formed the basis for the co-design workshops where findings were presented and considered by participants to inform development of interventions. These findings are summarised in Section 5.1.4.

❖ Stakeholder mapping and selection of participants for the co-design workshop

Stakeholder mapping was conducted ahead of the co-design workshop, informed by the outputs of the above-mentioned data synthesis workshops. Participants were purposively selected based on their influence, expertise, and vested interest. Representatives from those directly impacted by the interventions, such as PPW and HCWs were included. Many of these were among those that had participated in the formative studies. Stakeholders with decision-making power such as policymakers and health administrators were included to ensure their support in enacting and influencing change as needed, and to solicit their input in identifying other influential stakeholders. Several other stakeholder groups were identified and invited to participate include experts in public health, employers and health workers labour representatives, climate scientists, environmental health specialists and civil society organizations (CSOs).

Potential participants were grouped into the following clusters and recruiters ensured adequate representation of each group: 1. PPW; 2. Household heads; 3. Health workers; 4. Community; 5. Health system; 6. Sub-national and 7. National.

❖ Baseline findings shared in co-design workshops

The baseline study was conducted in two facilities at different levels of the healthcare pyramid: an urban community health centre (CHC) and an urban regional hospital in South Africa’s Tshwane district. Baseline assessments included in-depth interviews with 15 HCWs, 157 hours of observations, and 80 completed surveys. The thermal conditions in the healthcare facilities have been monitored since Autumn 2023. Key findings are presented below.

Thermal exposure in health facilities: The average apparent temperature in facilities was consistently in the caution range (26°C – 31°C). In the CHC, while average temperatures in the Admission and Antenatal wards were similar, the temperature range in the antenatal wards indicated spikes in temperature often in the extreme caution range. In the hospital, the neonatal ward was the hottest (average: 29.6°C) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Average apparent temperatures in health facilities in Tshwane, South Africa

This is further reflected through the surveys where 58% of respondents reported the temperature in their workplace as hot or very hot, and through IDIs where participants reported:

"We don't have...an air conditioner here or a fan. Our fan is not working. So you experience a lot of heat with the space"

HH_ZA-02-012_18Jan2024

"...other wards they are cooler than this one. This one it's a bomb"

HH_ZA-01-041_31Jan2024

Heat and healthcare worker physical wellbeing: A high proportion of healthcare workers reported being exhausted or so exhausted that they needed a break. Dehydration and discomfort were also reported in all settings. Effects of heat on physical wellbeing was more prevalent in clinic compared to hospital settings (Figure 2). In IDIs, similar themes emerged.

*"Because **when it's hot**, I mean, eish! Yoh! You get **tired easily**."*

HH_ZA_01_037_IDI_29Jan2024

*"Now this room is too hot and I'm getting hot here. I **cannot tolerate** to stay here in this hot temperature."*

HH-ZA_02_013_IDI 1Feb2024

*"...you **become dehydrated**, especially if you're too busy. Let's say on days where we have 13 to 15 deliveries, it's not like you have time to take many water breaks...Then you can become dehydrated or feel unwell."*

HH_ZA_01_001_IDI_07Feb2024

Figure 2. Impact of heat on physical health of health workers, South Africa

Heat and healthcare worker psychological wellbeing: Healthcare workers report heat being a contributor to mental exhaustion, irritability, and decreased cognitive function.

*"You get **exhausted mentally** and physically."*

HH-ZA-02-012_18Jan2024

"Yes, I do think heat affects your mental wellbeing."

HH_ZA_01_001_07Feb2024

*"...if you work in an uncomfortable temperature condition, **you get irritated easily.**"*

HH_ZA_01_039_30Jan2024

"It's just not easy to concentrate."

HH-ZA-01-039_30Jan2024

*"I think like any other human being, when the temperatures affect you at that time, **sometimes you forget**, you know? You forget some other aspects."*

HH-ZA-02-012_18Jan2024

*"We **get to be slow** neh? Let me just be honest. When it's hot, [but] especially in our ward,...The person who's writing will be slow."*

HH_ZA_01_039_30Jan2024

Heat and healthcare worker performance and quality of care: During IDIs, healthcare workers reported that the duration and timing of work-related activities was slower or were postponed to later in the afternoon, resulting in longer wait times for patients to receive care or procedures. In addition, some procedures were either rushed or not done at all, in an attempt to finish tasks and leave the place of work when it is too hot. Among survey respondents, 43% reported reduced work effort due to heat during the hot season. Communication was also affected by the heat: a) during the last heatwave, 40% reported observing poorer communication with patients every time or often, and b) 35% reported

observing poorer communication between healthcare workers every time or often.

*"...So maybe instead of taking maybe five minutes with the patient, it will take eight minutes because I'll be a little bit **slower due to the way I will be feeling the effect of heat at that time**... it will be added with two minutes or what. So there's going to be a **slight delay** on that one, **but the care is still the same.**"*

HH_ZA-01-007_IDI_23Jan2024

*"...let's say someone is from the other ward, labour ward, and we need to [do] vulva swabbing... So maybe it's around 1[pm] to 2[pm]...so we'll rather postpone... **So I will just postpone to at least 4:30[pm] to 5[pm] because it will be cooler** and easy to do it."*

*"All I'm thinking about at that point in time is just to get out of there. So, **some of the things that I need to do, I don't really do**...because of how **unbearable the heat is**, I will not even be having that patience to go there to teach, be patient with her. Because...**all I want to do is go sit down, maybe get myself some air or some ice** or whatever. But...if the heat was not as bad, I would be focusing more on the patient."*

HH_ZA_01-004_24Jan2024

*"...when it's hot, I think others [get] frustrated neh? And then you end up maybe **shouting** at the patient"*

HH_ZA_01_037_IDI_29Jan2024

*"There would be **less communication**...in the morning, you were asking long questions, then your **questions become shorter** during that period."*

HH_ZA_02_012_18Jan2024

Availability of heat adaptation measures: The survey asked about availability of water, functioning air conditioning, cold water, fans, and shading devices. While most reported adaptation measures being available, there was some variation between different adaptation measures (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Availability of heat adaptation measures MNCH wards in health facilities in Tshwane, South Africa

These findings highlight how high ambient temperatures, driven by climate change, are compromising the health, performance, and safety of clinical staff in antenatal, delivery and postnatal settings in Tshwane, South Africa; demonstrating the urgent need for heat adaptation strategies within health system.

❖ Co-design workshops

Our co-design workshop agenda was built around the Socio-Ecological Model (SEM) (Figure 4), which was used to structure the development of multi-layered heat adaptation interventions at multiple-levels with various stakeholders. The SEM recognises the interplay between multiple layers of influence—from individual behaviour to policy-level decisions—and allows us to craft nuanced interventions that account for cultural, environmental, and systemic factors unique to LMIC settings (Golden SD,2012). The model’s structure, which includes individuals, their immediate household, community, organizational (formal networks and services) and broader social, economic and policy levels, offers a holistic approach to tackling heat-related health challenges across diverse socioeconomic conditions (Fig 4). In South Africa's urban areas, which are characterised by informal housing and marked by systemic inequalities and infrastructural limitations, the SEM framework ensures that interventions can be culturally appropriate, feasible, and multi-layered (McLeroy KR, 1988). The co-

design workshop facilitators used the SEM to develop a conceptual model depicting environmental, social and structural drivers of heat health. This model was informed by both literature and key findings from the study and was presented to participants during the workshop.

Figure 4. Social Ecological Model depicting key drivers of heat health

The co-design workshop was conducted over three consecutive days from 29th to 31st July 2024. Participants were divided into groups to minimise power imbalances that may have inhibited participation. The following engagements were undertaken:

- ❖ Day 1: Engagement with pregnant and postpartum women.
- ❖ Day 2: Engagement with broader stakeholders, including community leaders, heads of households, civil society, health workers, and health system representatives.
- ❖ Day 3: Synthesis of interventions and refinement of the ToC with all stakeholders, followed by consensus building and feedback sessions.

❖ Day 1: Engagement with Pregnant and Postpartum Women

The first day centred around gathering insights from pregnant and postpartum women in Laudium, Pretoria. The workshop environment was designed to be inclusive, with babysitting services and private breastfeeding booths, ensuring participants felt comfortable and engaged. A total of 21 women, many with their babies attended the workshop. The following activities were undertaken.

- **Community Resource Mapping (CRM):**

Three groups were formed for this activity to create maps for the three areas including Laudium CBD, and the two locations Itireleng and Mooiplaas, where the women live. Participants sketched their localities, identifying areas most affected by heat. The resulting sketched maps included details such as key landmarks, roads and facilities, as well as hotspots which participants believe to be the areas where people experience the most heat in those communities (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Women participating in the CRM activity, South Africa

- **Presentation of Key study Findings:** The results of the study were presented to participants using simplified illustrations to explain the key findings. The researchers explained the findings and participants engaged and asked questions during the presentation.
- **Identification of Interventions:** Participants engaged in a group session to identify Interventions needed to combat the effect of heat within the different locations as identified during the CRM. The women placed different icons provided to them to show the different types of interventions (personal/ behavioural, intervention in homes or in the community).

- **Ranking and Prioritization of Interventions:** The women were then guided by the facilitators to rank the interventions by allocating points (1 to 5) to each activity, considering importance and practicality. Each listed intervention was ranked by the group and presented back in plenary. Priority interventions with scores of 3-5 points were added to the maps indicating where within the community such interventions were needed.

❖ **Day 2: Engagement with Broader Stakeholders**

On the second day, 101 participants, including household heads, community stakeholders, CSOs, and government representatives (local, provincial, and national levels from the department of health, department of fisheries, forestry and environment, department of agriculture, department of public works, department of human settlements), gathered to continue the co-design process. The day began with a presentation of the outcomes from Day 1, followed by group activities. The groups were divided into four: 1. Households 2. Community 3. Health workers 4. Health system/ National/ sub-national

- **Presentation of Study Findings:** The first two groups (households and community) were initially allocated one venue where the results from the HAPI study were presented to them. The other two groups (HCWs and Health systems/Nation/sub-national) also remained together for the presentation of key findings from both the HAPI and HIGH Horizons studies.

Following the presentations, participants went to their assigned group venues where they engaged in specific activities as per unique program for each group. The following activities were undertaken by the different groups.

- **Community Mapping:** The household heads and community groups were guided to undertake the CRM activity similar to Day 1 participants. This highly engaging activity enable participants in each of the groups to identify important landmarks and hotspots in their communities where people experience heat the most. Once the sketched maps had been completed, participants marked

the heat-affected areas and then proceeded to brainstorm and identify potential interventions that could be implemented to mitigate the impact of heat on residents.

- **SWOT Analysis:** The Health Workers and the Health systems group used the SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis to examine current challenges and opportunities for adaptation to heat in healthcare settings. Both groups engaged in extensive discussions to identify these elements. Upon completing the SWOT analysis, participants in both groups worked together to brainstorm potential interventions needed to address the weakness and threats as well as capitalise on the opportunities available to enhance heat mitigation.
- **Generating a list of priority interventions:** Following the brainstorming sessions by the groups to identify potential interventions, group members started building a list of interventions, categorised into the following groupings: Awareness-raising; Behaviour change; Nature-based solutions; Built environment modification; Health workforce resilience and Health system adaptations.
- **Ranking of interventions:** All four groups were guided by their facilitators to rank the identified interventions using a criteria that considered importance, practicality and cost of implementation. All four groups engaged extensively, deliberating on which interventions are most important and practical, and for which target group. The health worker group was instructed to focus mainly on interventions relevant to health workers, and to identify what would be most important to that group of stakeholders.

Following identification of interventions, the groups ranked each one based on their assessment and rating of practicality, feasibility and importance. The ranking was based on a Likert scale of 1-5 with 1 being least desirable and 5 being the most desirable score. The ranked lists were generated after determining total scores (or in some groups, average scores) for each intervention.

❖ **Day 3: Synthesis and Finalization of the Theory of Change**

The third and final day of the workshop focused on synthesizing the outputs from the previous two days and refining the draft ToC. The workshop began with a recap of the Day 2 activities. The key activities of Day 3 included the following:

- **Feedback by groups on Priority Interventions:** Each group was given an opportunity to provide brief feedback on their engagements and to present their proposed interventions and ranked lists. The audience engaged with each presentation and questions were asked and emerging issues discussed.
- **Presentation of the Draft ToC:** The facilitators presented the initial draft of the ToC, which had been developed using the workshop outputs from Day 1 and 2 and background information. Participants were explained about the theoretical concept of ToC, explaining its components and the logic behind the approach. The differences between TOCs and Log-frames or Results framework, as well as the overall anatomy of the ToC was discussed.
- **Group Work on Refining the ToC:** Participants were tasked with refining the draft ToC, focusing on confirming the preconditions/outcomes, identifying key assumptions, and engaging in discussions to determine the necessary interventions needed to achieve the desired outcomes. Each group worked on refining preconditions for resilience-building interventions at various levels—individual, household, community, health workforce, and health system.
- **Plenary Discussions of the ToC:** After group work, the participants returned to plenary to present their refinements. The outputs were debated and agreed upon, ensuring consensus on the final ToC.
- **Final Session on Next Steps:** The session concluded with the project leadership outlining the next steps, which included finalizing the ToC, developing a detailed log frame, and planning the implementation of pilot interventions.

5.2 Co-design process in Zimbabwe

❖ Overview of approach

The co-design process began with a participatory stakeholder analysis workshop in July 2024 in Zimbabwe to identify key stakeholders for inclusion in subsequent co-design workshops. A series of co-design workshops were conducted between December 2024 and completed in January 2025. The process involved engagement with key stakeholders to develop heat adaptation interventions for pregnant women and their babies in Mt Darwin District. Additionally, the process explored climate adaptation mitigation interventions in healthcare facilities with the primary focus being to improve the wellbeing, performance, and quality of care provided by healthcare workers. The use of interdisciplinary scientific methodologies with stakeholder input was designed to create cost-effective and locally relevant solutions.

The first workshop gathered PPWs, partners, and community leaders to ensure interventions were culturally relevant and locally supported. The second workshop involved healthcare workers, facility managers, and public infrastructure departments to address health system risks and integrate climate resilience. The third workshop engaged policymakers to align interventions with governance and funding structures, while the final session consolidated findings from all groups to refine the intervention package.

❖ Baseline data synthesis

Prior to the co-design workshop, data synthesis sessions were held in July 2024, in preparation for the co-design workshop. The workshop was done with the research team members from both HIGH Horizons and HAPI Projects. The data synthesis integrated findings from the data collected in the HIGH Horizons project and the formative stage of the HAPI study. This includes data from sources shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Summary of Data Sources used for data synthesis in Zimbabwe

Source	HAPI	Population focus	HIGH Horizons	Population focus
Participant observations	X	Pregnant and postpartum women	X	HCWs
IDIs	X	Pregnant and postpartum women (serial)	X	HCWs
KIIs	X	Health officials, community leaders	X	Health officials, policymakers
Photovoice	-	-	X	Pregnant and postpartum women Village health workers
Transect walk	-	-	X	Pregnant and postpartum women
Diary accounts	X	Pregnant and postpartum women	-	-
Health Worker Survey	-	-	X	HCWs
Health Worker Time motion			X	HCWs
Thermal simulations	X	Household and health facility	X	Health facility only
Physiological metrics from Fitbit trackers, core body and iButton temperature monitors	X	Pregnant and postpartum women (no core body temperature)	X	HCWs

❖ Stakeholder mapping and selection of participants for the co-design workshop

A thorough mapping exercise was carried out to identify the key stakeholders involved in the co-design process. This exercise categorized stakeholders across various domains, including individual, household, community, health facility, district/provincial, national/policy, and international levels. The process considered the suggested interventions, relevant stakeholders and power dynamics from the formative studies. The mapping also highlighted the interconnections and "connector" roles between these stakeholder categories, emphasizing their interdependence and the flow of influence across levels. For instance, individuals were identified as critical links to households, with household

heads acting as key conduits to the broader community. Similarly, village leaders and community health workers played pivotal roles in connecting communities to health facilities. This hierarchical connectivity extended further, linking districts to provinces, provinces to national entities, and national entities to international stakeholders. Stakeholders then participated in mapping through a power interest matrix that classified the participants by interest and power to develop stakeholder lists for the Community, Health Systems and Policy Workshops (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Stakeholders taking part in mapping using the power interest matrix, Zimbabwe

❖ **Baseline findings shared in co-design workshops**

The co-design workshops provided a platform for the research team to disseminate formative findings on the studies done to investigate the effects of heat on both the healthcare worker and the pregnant and postpartum women. The negative impacts of heat on HCW's wellbeing, performance, quality of care, and physical and mental health, as well as the current adaptation strategies, were discussed.

The formative study findings showed that extreme temperatures had adverse effects on the quality of care provided by the HCWs on their patients (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Effects of heat on quality of care, Zimbabwe

HCW expressed that they tend to focus more on getting respite from the heat than attending to their patients.

*"Quality is compromised when you are in a hot environment because your **focus tends to shift towards finding ways to escape the discomfort**. For example, if you are working in a hot room, you may feel rushed and try to expedite the process. In doing so, you might inadvertently **miss important points** or overlook patient complaints."*

IDI ZW-DO-05-3

The formative study also found that high temperatures have negative impacts on the physical health of HCWs. The visual summary (Figure 8) illustrates the burden of occupational heat stress on HCWs revealing clear physiological and wellbeing

impacts consistent with climate-related health risk pathways. The majority reported severe thermal discomfort, including high levels of sweating, fatigue, dehydration, and heat-induced malaise, with one in four experiencing symptoms consistent with heat stroke. These findings highlight how rising ambient temperatures, driven by climate change, are compromising the health, performance, and safety of frontline clinical staff, necessitating urgent adaptation strategies within health system.

Figure 8. Impact of heat on the physical health of HCWs, Zimbabwe

When it's extremely hot, I tire quickly, I'm thirsty, and my mouth gets really dry, I get up slowly because of light-headedness and fatigue. My attention on the woman delivering suffers.

ZW-MT-06-0

The formative findings also indicate that HCWs were mostly dehydrated because of the high temperatures in their working environment (Table 2). Dehydration was measured in USG **80% > 1.015**, our dehydration threshold (Figure 9). The study findings indicate that the majority of HCWs were dehydrated during their working shifts and had few water sources.

Table 2. HCW Urine Specific Gravity, Zimbabwe

Mean	Min	Max	USG >1.015	USG <1.015
1.023	1.003	1.043	80%	20%

Figure 9. HCW Urine Specific Gravity, Zimbabwe

“Sometimes we don’t have water to drink here at work, so you are always dehydrated, and as a result, you become rude to patients or not perform your duties well.”

ZW-MT-04-6

The formative findings also show that extreme temperatures negatively affected the cognitive functions of HCWs. Specifically, symptoms such as forgetfulness, increased irritations, and anxiety were found consistently reported by HCWs during the hot season (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Anxiety levels amongst HCW, Zimbabwe

Minimal 22(50%), Mild 16 (36%), Moderate 6 (14%)
 (0/4=1 "Minimal") (5/9=2 "Mild") (10/14=3 "Moderate")
 (15/21=4 "Severe")

"It's difficult to concentrate because your brain will be exhausted already, as I said before, you will continue working but at a slow rate, or confused, or end up repeating what you have written before, because your brain had been exposed to the sun, I don't know what happens really when you are tired but, it affects documentation.... "

ZW-MT-11-7

HCWs also indicated that they were vulnerable to effects such as clinical errors due to their exposure to high temperatures.

The formative findings on pregnant and postpartum women showed how the impact of heat affected them in their homes, cognizant of their roles and responsibilities as rural housewives. For impactful presentations, some of the recruited women attended the co-design workshops and guided by their diaries, gave firsthand testimonies of their interaction with heat, which included difficulties in sleeping, excessive sweating, and swollen feet. For the babies, skin rashes, irritations, and diarrheal diseases were noted as some of the impacts of heat.

❖ Co-design workshops

The co-design workshops were embedded in the Socio-Ecological Model (SEM) as the basis for the development of multi-layered heat adaptation-mitigation interventions at multi-levels with various stakeholders including Individual, Organizational, Community, and Policy levels. In the workshops participants were divided into groups to minimise power imbalances that would potentially inhibit participation. This methodical approach facilitated an exhaustive exploration of heat adaptation interventions, extending from grassroots initiatives to overarching national policies. The workshops' lead facilitators underwent rigorous training, which prepared them to steer the participants through discussions, succinctly summarizing the processes and insights gleaned from the formative stage.

The workshops were conducted in a mix of local languages, including English and Shona, and documented through audio recordings complemented by written note. The co-design workshops were conducted and facilitated in person in an active workshop-style setting, recognising the importance of giving equal time and encouraging contributions by all participants. The facilitation team outlined the workshop objectives, emphasizing that everyone's experience and perceptions were key to the development of appropriate interventions (Figure 11).

A thorough discussion of the interventions that had been proposed in the formative stage of the research underwent further review during the plenary sessions of the co-design workshops. The participants were invited to add to the long list any other interventions that they felt were missing from the original list but which they envisaged as worth further exploring. A scoring and ranking process utilizing a prioritization method was used, where each of the participants was allocated three pebbles and tasked with placing them on the interventions, they deemed most crucial in having a more responsive approach to heat impacts.

Figure 11. Research Team facilitating the community co-design workshop convened at Mt Darwin school, Zimbabwe

The community workshop was held on the 5th of December 2025. A diverse group of 23 stakeholders participated in the community co-design workshop, including community leaders such as chiefs and village heads, government department representatives, NGO representatives, healthcare workers, community members (including pregnant and postpartum women), and technical experts from various sectors.

The Health System and Policy workshops were held as parallel workshops and the consolidate workshop which included all the three groups (Community, Health systems and Policy) was held on the 21st of January 2025. The health system workshop was attended by 20 stakeholders, including representatives from local Government, Public Service Commission, the Meteorological Services Department, Forestry Commission, Pfura Rural District Council, Ministry of Health and Child Care, the Ministry of Public Works and other representatives drawn from the community and healthcare facilities. Participants reviewed the interventions identified during the formative stage, suggested additional ones they found necessary, and then voted and ranked them to create a prioritized list of interventions. The Policy group had 21 stakeholders which included a wide range

of policymakers from different backgrounds in the Zimbabwean policymaking context and in Mt Darwin in particular. Among these were the Local Government officials, Public Service Commission, the Meteorological Services Department, Forestry Commission, Pfura Rural District Council, Pfura District Development Coordinator, Chief Dotito, Ministry of Health and Child Care, the Ministry of Public Works, Youth Representatives, Environmental Management Agency, representatives from the African Union, Institute of Sustainability and Development Finance, World Health Organisation, Grow A Tree Foundation, Nehanda Radio and TV. The policymakers were invited to add, a long list of interventions that was informed by the formative data collection conducted in Mt. Darwin, followed by a rigorous data analysis process. The workshop's facilitators highlighted how an extensive literature review supported the scientific rationale behind the proposed interventions, underscoring the evidence-based approach taken in the development of these interventions.

The consolidation workshop engaged 38 participants drawn from the three codesign workshops i.e. community, health systems as well as policy. These participants were involved in evaluating the prioritized interventions across 11 variables namely feasibility, acceptability, affordability, cultural sensitivity, perceived risk of heat, health burden, community participation, livelihood impact of the intervention, equity in vulnerability, climate/geography appropriateness as well as availability of legal/policy framework against or supporting such interventions. Each intervention underwent assessment for appropriateness, rated on a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 10, with 1 representing the least favourable and 10 signifying high effectiveness. The results were organized and summarized based on intervention level, total scores, and average scores per group for each intervention.

6 Adaptation interventions selected for implementation

This section details the adaptation interventions selected for implementation in South Africa and Zimbabwe, following the co-design process and further refinement by the study team.

The interventions will be implemented in the same facilities as for the baseline study. These include: Mamelodi Regional Hospital and Stanza Bopape Community Health Centre in South Africa, Mt Darwin District Hospital, Chitse Rural Healthcare Clinic and Dotito Rural Healthcare Clinic in Zimbabwe. An additional facility is added in South Africa because it participates in the mitigation activities: Laudium CHC.

The beneficiaries of the interventions are the same as for the baseline study (i.e. healthcare workers at all levels in the maternal and newborn health related departments in the facilities where HIGH Horizons works). The main target group for the intervention is HCWs and other staff active in maternity units and neonatal wards in the selected facilities, as for the baseline study.

Tables 3 and 4 summarise the interventions and problems addressed in South Africa and Zimbabwe, respectively.

6.1 South Africa

Table 3. Climate adaptation interventions selected through the co-design process in South Africa

Type of intervention	Intervention component in South Africa	Problems addressed
Human resources / behaviour	<p>Heat Champion (2 per facilities) Their duties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health talks to PPW and HCW • Distribute IEC materials • Aircon controls • Ventilation checks, • Provision of H2O to HCW • Water cooler refilling • Provide HCWs with personal cooling items, such as cooling towels, vests, or fans • Use posters, flyers, and brief educational meetings to emphasise the risks of heat stress and dehydration • Indoor thermal monitoring • Monitoring heat stress symptoms/incidents among HCW • Present a tray of cooling device options for personal use (small rechargeable fan, additional water, cooling vest) • Check functioning of cooling devices in facility • Number of HCWs receiving guidance or interventions from the Heat Champion per month • Encourage HCWs to take water breaks during shifts • Encourage a buddy system where HCWs remind each other to drink water, take breaks, and stay cool • Monitor usage of hydration stations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of HCW awareness and education on the impact of heat on their health • Lack of HCW awareness on available adaptation interventions • Lack of access to Heat Health IEC materials • Suboptimal/Incorrect use of air conditioner • Limited access to clean and safe water as HCWs do not take water breaks and do not trust water sources
Equipment / behavioural change	<p>Provide water filter cooler Details:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2-3 water filters per clinic providing cool drinking water for HCW during hot weather in ideal locations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of access to safe and clean water • Dehydration in HCWs on duty

Type of intervention	Intervention component in South Africa	Problems addressed
Building / thermal conditions	Air conditioners Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solar-powered/low emission/energy efficient air conditioners installed in Stanza CHC (antenatal care waiting room) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of air conditioners in some areas of Stanza CHC, e.g. ANC • Sub-optimal use of air conditioners where available at Stanza CHC • However: Air conditioners powered by electricity and contributing to high gas emissions
	Reflective roof paint Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of ideal locations and acceptable colour for application of reflective roof paint at Laudium CHC, Stanza CHC and Mamelodi Hospital MNH service points • Purchase reflective paint for the roofs of Laudium CHC, Stanza CHC and Mamelodi Hospital 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High indoor temperatures in MNH service points due to non-reflection of heat in uncoated roofs
	Roof/Ceiling insulation Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Install roof insulation at ANC, Labour and Neonates in Stanza CHC and possibly Laudium • Secure quotes, purchase and install insulation in roofs of Stanza and/or Laudium CHC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High indoor temperatures in MNH areas at Stanza CHC due to uninsulated roofs
Monitoring / policy	Occupational health standards assessment Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review Occupational Health Standard (OHS) indicators for health facility compliance • Define 2 heat indicators for inclusion as part of OHS facility compliance • Assess the current compliance levels at Stanza and Laudium CHCs and Mamelodi Hospital with established OHS indicators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heat indicators are not included/incorporated into routine reporting at facilities
Nature / thermal conditions	Planting trees Details: At least 50 trees planted in Stanza Bopape CHC and Mamelodi Hospital in high traffic areas accessible to MNH HCWs (e.g. in close proximity to wards)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of trees and vegetation increase heat islands in facilities • Lack of tree shading for HCWs

6.2 Zimbabwe

Table 4. Climate adaptation interventions selected through the co-design process in Zimbabwe

Type of intervention	Intervention component in Zimbabwe	Problems addressed
Behaviour/ Individual	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phone based Heat EWS • Signage reminders to maintain hydration • Buddy system • Adjusting work schedules • Training on heat related conditions • Personal cooling kits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of heat management • Lack of knowledge of impending heat waves/ high temperatures • Dehydration in HCW on duty • Dehydration in HCW on duty • Dehydration and lack of heat management • Lack of knowledge of heat-related conditions, including heat exhaustion and heatstroke. Dehydration and lack of heat management
Behaviour / Facility-level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ANC Heat-Health talks • Heat management training • Indoor thermal monitoring • Waste segregation • Heat champions - EHTs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of knowledge of heat-related conditions, including heat exhaustion and heatstroke • As above • Dehydration • Waste mismanagement • Lack of heat management
Behaviour / Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop facility guidance to support heat-health training, heat-adaptive work schedules, rests, lightweight clothing and heatwave emergencies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of knowledge of heat-related conditions, including heat exhaustion and heatstroke • Dehydration • Lack of heat management
Built environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Install solar-powered, energy-efficient air conditioners in ANC waiting rooms. • Construct shaded rest areas, such as thatched outdoor spaces, for HCWs. • Enhance ventilation in MNH workstations using louvres and cross-ventilation systems. • Apply reflective paint on roofs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of air conditioning in ANC facilities • Lack of shaded areas for HCWs to take breaks during extreme heat • High indoor temperatures • High indoor temperatures due to non-reflection of heat in uncoated roofs • High indoor temperatures • Dehydration; Lack consistent water supply

Type of intervention	Intervention component in Zimbabwe	Problems addressed
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use thermal mass construction materials in Dotito to regulate indoor temperatures. • Install 20,000L water storage tanks at the district hospital • Install solar-powered systems for water supply and cooling at all three sites. • Establish a demonstration site at Dotito to showcase heat-resilient infrastructure, mitigation and adaptation strategies. • Deploy solar-powered energy-efficient lighting, refrigeration systems, and low-global-warming refrigerants and inhalers • SOP guidance on heat-resilient building standards ventilation protocols and energy-efficient procurement through SOPs and collaboration with ministries 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of heat management; Dehydration; Lack consistent water supply • Lack of heat management; Lack of built environment that ensures proper heat management and indoor temperatures • High carbon emissions due to refrigerants; High usage/dependence on energy inefficient lighting; High carbon emissions due to refrigerants and high energy consuming equipment • High indoor temperatures
Nature-based	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Plant indigenous, fast-growing, drought-resistant trees in high-traffic areas near wards to provide shade • Develop facility guidance to support tree planting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of trees and vegetation increase heat islands in facilities • Lack of tree shading for HCWs

7 Theory of Change

Figures 12 and 13 present the theories of change for both countries, South Africa and Zimbabwe.

7.1 South Africa

Figure 12. Co-design in South Africa: Adaptation interventions and ToC

7.2 Zimbabwe

Figure 13. Co-design in Zimbabwe: Adaptation interventions and ToC

8 Progress to date

A timeline detailing the proposed implementation of interventions is provided in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Timeline for implementation and evaluation of adaptation interventions in South Africa and Zimbabwe

	2024				2025												2026							
	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	March	April	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	March	April	May	June	July	Aug
Hot months (South Africa)																								
Hot months (Zimbabwe)																								
Implementation of adaptation interventions																								
SOUTH AFRICA																								
* Implementation of facility-based Heat Champion																								
* Purchase of cooling vests																								
* Procurement and installation of air conditioners																								
* Procurement and installation of water filter coolers																								
* Procurement and installation of roof insulation																								
* Procurement of reflective roof paint and painting roofs																								
* Identify ideal areas for planting trees and plant the trees in these areas																								
* Incorporate Heat Indicators in Occupational Health Standards for Health Facilities																								
ZIMBABWE																								
Individual behavioural interventions																								
* Individual HCW heat health participatory engagement																								
* LED Boards																								
* Heat Champions (e.g. Environmental Health Technicians/Village Health Workers)																								
* EWS through the MotherHeat Alert Application & Healthcare Workers																								
* Heat health talks																								
* Buddie system																								
* Personal cooling kits																								
* Hydration station (Installation of water dispensers)																								
Built environment interventions																								
* Water storage tanks																								
* Cool roofs																								
* Cool floors																								
* Ward aesthetics																								
* Solar water pump																								
Nature-based interventions																								
* Tree planting at facility																								
Policy interventions																								
* Guidelines on reflective paint																								
* Guidelines for institutionalising EWS																								
Evaluation of adaptation interventions																								
Process evaluation																								
Impact evaluation																								
Continuous thermal monitoring																								
Analysis of impact (endline)																								
Dissemination																								

8.1 South Africa

Protocol amendment: In South Africa, the protocol amendment detailing the evaluation of the selected interventions at health facilities was aligned with the LSHTM protocol and finalised in January 2025.

Regulatory Submissions: The protocol was submitted and approved by the University of the Witwatersrand Human Research Ethics Committee in February 2025. The protocol has also been uploaded onto the SA Clinical Trials Registry because the study involves an intervention implementation.

Implementation of interventions: The implementation of interventions has begun and will continue in stages during the cooler months of 2025. All implementations are expected to be in place by October 2025, in time for initiation of endline evaluation activities. To date, we have planted 58 trees at the health facilities. We are currently conducting stakeholder engagements to obtain written approvals from facility and district management and the Department of Public Works, for the implementation of building interventions. We are also in the process of finalising contracts for roof painting and ceiling insulation at facilities. Training on the use of reflective roof paints was conducted with the site team on the 17th of March 2025, in preparation for implementation during the drier winter months. Quotes for energy efficient air conditioners, water filter coolers and cooling vests have been obtained, and these will be ordered closer to the anticipated time of implementation. The heat champion has been hired and will serve as the point person for all implementation activities. Over the next few months, the heat champion will integrate themselves into the facility and acquainting themselves and work with the Climate team with processes, such that the implementation on interventions fits in with facility procedures as seamlessly as possible.

8.2 Zimbabwe

Implementation of interventions will commence on the 1st of June 2025. Tree donations have been received from the Forestry Commission, a key collaborating parastatal whose mandate is to regulate and manage the sustainable utilisation of forest resources in the country. The trees will be planted at identified community sites, including households as well as facilities as part of the identified nature-based interventions.

Approvals for the construction of a demonstration maternity ward at Dotito clinic have been obtained from the Department of Public Works, the agency responsible for managing government properties, buildings and infrastructure. Construction of the demonstration maternity ward is expected to be completed by June 2025. Approvals were also obtained for the implementation of facility interventions which were finalised from the co-design workshops. Site visits were conducted at the three facilities in collaboration with engineers from the Department of Public Works at both the district and provincial levels. Representatives from the Forestry Commission and the Ministry of Health and Child Care also participated in the site visit.

Immediate next steps include conducting topographic surveys and soil tests at the maternity ward demonstration site. The design brief, in collaboration with relevant stakeholders, is currently underway.

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